

Case Study Requirements Specification:

Martian Spacecraft Management System

1 Introduction

This document is a Software Requirements Specification (SRS) for the Management System for Martian transport craft. This SRS is the result of interviews with the body responsible for organizing intergalactic transport. This specification has been made according to the "IEEE Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specification ANSI/IEEE 1993" standard.

The case study consists of 3 exercises that are developed incrementally. You shouldn't move on to exercise 2 until you make sure that exercise 1 works perfectly, nor move to exercise 3 until exercise 2 doesn't work perfectly. **The important thing about exercise is not that you finish everything, but that what you do, you do well.**

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of the specification is to clearly and precisely define all the functionalities and constraints of the system you want to build. The document is addressed to the development team.

1.2 Scope of the system

The future system will be called SIGEM (Martian Spacecraft Management System), and aims to automate the control of cargoes and discharges from transport ships, which is currently carried out by hand. These transport ships transport Martians from an origin mothership to a destination mothership.

2 Overview

This section presents us with an overview of the system, in order to know the main functions that must be performed, the associated data, the restrictions imposed and any factors that may affect the development of the same.

2.1 System functions

In space there are many transport aircraft to move Martians between different motherships. These aircraft are a kind of martian buses between different motherships (where the Martians live). The system must manage the movements that martians make in aircraft to reach the motherships.

The functionality of the system can be summarized in these three points:

- Create mothership
- Create Aircraft

- Manage passengers
- Review aircraft

2.1.1 Create mothership

This functionality stores the data of existing motherships. Of each mothership you only want to store the name and an identifier.

2.1.2 Create Aircraft

This functionality is intended to store all existing aircraft. The aircraft will go from an origin mothership to a destination mothership (origin and destination may be the same mothership on some occasions). An aircraft card such as the one shown in the "Aircraft" annex is stored in the system.

2.1.3 Manage passengers

Different passengers get on and off an aircraft. The system must provide the functionality to record passengers boarding the aircraft and passengers getting off. Each time a passenger boards an aircraft, the information in the "Assign Passenger" Annex must be entered into the system. Each time a passenger gets off the aircraft upon arrival at the destination, in the system you must enter the information shown in the Annex "Download passenger". No more passengers may board than the maximum allowed.

2.1.4 Review aircraft

Once a day, a reviewer enters all the aircraft and checks that the Martians have paid for the ticket. This also serves to keep track of the Martians that had climbed at that time on the aircraft. Only one reviewer can enter each aircraft per day. For each revision, the system must store the information displayed in the "Revision" Annex.

2.2 User characteristics

The system will be used by general direction of space traffic (DGTE) workers, who are responsible for directing all intergalactic traffic.

3 Specific Requirements

3.1 Create mothership

Tickets

Of each mothership only the name and an identifier are stored. _

Process

Motherships are like floating cities where Martians live. Multiple motherships can be created as time progresses.

Exit

The data of the mothership is recorded in the system. DGTE workers should be able to consult the list of existing motherships.

3.2 Create Aircraft

Entrance

The data to be entered are an Id for the aircraft, a name, the maximum number of Martians it can carry, the mothership from which it departs (origin) and the mothership towards which it is going (destination). All the information to be entered is represented in the Annex "Aircraft".

Process

Aircraft are created to make the route between two motherships carrying Martians. In some cases, aircraft are created so that martian tourists can make tours of space, and in these cases, the mothership to and from the spacecraft is the same.

Exit

The data of the new aircraft is stored in the system. DGTE employees can consult the list of existing aircraft.

3.3 Manage passengers

Entrance

Passenger management includes two functionalities: assigning a passenger to the aircraft and getting a passenger off the aircraft. To assign a passenger to the aircraft you need the Id of the passenger and the ID of the aircraft on which it has been uploaded. All this information can be seen in the Annex "Assign passenger". If the passenger is not registered in the system, it must be created before assigning it to the aircraft. To create the passenger, only an ID and its name are required. To record that a passenger has got off the aircraft when it arrives at its destination, it is sufficient to indicate in the system the Id of the aircraft and the Id of the passenger, as it appears in the Annex "Download passenger".

Process

Passengers get on and off the aircraft when they reach a mothership. When a passenger boards the aircraft, this information must be recorded in the system. One restriction is that no more passengers can board an aircraft than the maximum number of Martians allowed for that aircraft. When a passenger gets off because he or she has arrived at the mothership destination, this information must be stored as well. In this way, the passenger information on each of the aircraft is always up to date.

Exit

The information of passengers who are currently on an aircraft must be up to date at all times. In addition, the list must indicate the number of passengers currently on the aircraft. DGTE employees can consult the list of passengers on each of the aircraft.

3.4 Review aircraft

Entrance

The form to be filled in is the one shown in the Annex "Revision". In this form you must fill in the Id of the reviewer, the name of the reviewer, the ID of the revised aircraft, the date on which the review occurs and the list of passengers that were currently on the aircraft.

Process

Once a day, a reviewer employed by the DGTE is uploaded on each of the aircraft and records in a history the passengers that are currently on the aircraft. The system should only allow for a single review per day for each aircraft. When posting the revision to the system, the user only enters the revision ID, the reviewer's name, the revised aircraft ID, and the date. The list of all Martians on the aircraft should be obtained automatically based on the information already in the system (previously, the Martians have been assigned as passengers and have not yet got off the aircraft). The information on the Revision tab is stored in the system as a history (that is, even if the Martian subsequently gets off the aircraft, the information that it was traveling on the aircraft at the time of the review must remain stored). This information is useful for controlling the movements of Martians between different motherships over time.

Exit

A history in which dgte employees can list the passengers that were per aircraft at the time of making the review. In addition to passenger and aircraft information, the date on which the review occurred should be shown.

4 Annex

Aircraft:

AIRCRAFT	
ID_AIRCRAFT	
NAME_AIRCRAFT	
MAX_NUMBER_MARTIANS	
STARTING_POINT_TRIP	END_POINT_TRIP

Assign passenger:

ASSIGN_PASSENGER

ID_PASSENGER

ID_AIRCRAFT

Get off passenger:

GET_OFF_PASSENGER

ID_PASSENGER

ID_AIRCRAFT

Review:

REVIEW

ID_REVIEW

NAME_REVIEWER

ID_REVISSED_AIRCRAFT

DATE

LIST OF MARTIANS ON BOARD THE AIRCRAFT

ID_MARTIAN_1

ID_MARTIAN_2

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ID_MARTIAN_3